

Constitution of a Mannan from the Kernel of Palmyra Palm Nut

C. V. N. Rao and A. K. Mukherjee

The kernel of Palmyra palm nut contains a galactomannan and a mannan, the latter being extracted with 18% NaOH solution. Hydrolysis of the fully methylated mannan yields 2,3,4,6-tetra-, 2,3,6-tri-, and 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose in the molar ratio of 1:9.15:1.12. These data are in agreement with those of periodate oxidation results. The structural significance of these results has been discussed.

The water-soluble polysaccharide from the green Palmyra palm nut (*Borassus flabellifer*, Linn.) has been shown to be a galactomannan¹ containing galactose and mannose in the molar ratio of 1:2.4. After extracting with water, the residue was extracted successively with 4% and 18% alkali solutions in an atmosphere of nitrogen (as it is known that alkali in presence of oxygen degrades polysaccharides, especially the partially oxidised ones²). The extracts were acidified (*pH* 4.5) with acetic acid and added to acetone to yield the polysaccharides. The 4% alkali extract (polysaccharide B) was found to give both mannose and galactose on hydrolysis, whereas the 18% alkali-extracted one (polysaccharide C) gave only mannose. The yields of polysaccharide C increased with the age of the nut.

This communication reports the structural studies of the mannan extracted from an old nut. The material was purified through copper complex with Fehling's solution³.

The mannan, $[\alpha]_{20}^D -43^\circ$ (in 18% NaOH solution) was methylated first by repeated treatment with dimethyl sulphate and alkali⁴ and then by Purdie's method⁵. The resulting methylated product showed no hydroxyl band in the IR spectrum and was a glassy solid: -OMe 42.83%. $[\alpha]_{20}^D -17^\circ$ (in chloroform). After methanolysis and hydrolysis of the methylated polysaccharide and hydrolysis of the resulting mixture of methyl glycosides, the mixture of methyl sugars, so obtained on paper chromatographic examination using solvents B and D, showed the presence of three methyl sugars. The mixture, which on demethylation yielded only D-mannose along with other partially demethylated sugars, was separated on Whatman No. 3MM filter papers into their components. These were eluted with water and dried. The tetra-, tri-, and di-*O*-methyl sugars were found to be in the molar ratio of 1:7.9:1.05.

The tetramethyl sugar fraction, $[\alpha]_{20}^D -2^\circ$ (in water) was shown to be 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-mannose through the preparation of its crystalline anilide⁶. The trimethyl

1. Mukherjee *et al.*, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 1409.

2. Banderet and Ronby, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, **30**, 1190.

3. Chanda *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1289; Glaudemans and Timell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 1200.

4. Haworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 8.

5. Purdie and Irvine, *ibid.*, 1903, **83**, 1021.

6. Irvine and McNicoll, *ibid.*, 1910, **87**, 1449.

sugar fraction, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -9^\circ$ (in water) was characterised as 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose by preparing the crystalline 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose-1,4-di-*p*-nitrobenzate⁷. The di-*O*-methyl sugar fraction having $[\alpha]_D^{20} -15^\circ$, was characterised to be 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose by conversion to 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-mannonic acid phenylhydrazide⁸.

The relative proportion of 2,3,4,6-tetra-, 2,3,6-tri-, and 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose, as estimated by hypiodite titration⁹ after separation on filter sheets using solvent D, was found to be 1:8.15:1.12. This ratio is in good agreement with that obtained during paper chromatographic separation of the mixture.

From the above results it is possible to assign a structure to the mannan. Demonstration of the presence of 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-mannose in comparatively large amounts shows that the mannan is considerably branched and the non-reducing ends of the molecule consist of mannopyranose residues.

The characterisation of 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose in the hydrolysate of the methylated mannan indicates that the backbone of the molecule is made up of 1 → 4 linked mannopyranose residues.

The identification of the 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose shows that at the branch points of the molecule, the mannose residues are linked through C₁, C₄, and C₆.

From the ratio of the amounts of tetra-, tri-, and di-*O*-methyl sugars, the length of the repeating unit of the polysaccharide works out to be 10.27 hexose units.

The mannan was oxidised with sodium metaperiodate at 15°. It was observed that one molar proportion of formic acid was liberated from every 9.7 anhydrohexose units in 25 hours and that each hexose unit consumed 1.05 moles of periodate at the same time. Accepting the structure deduced from methylation studies, one mole of formic acid should be liberated by 10.27 anhydrohexopyranose residues and each such unit should reduce 1.09 moles of periodate. Thus the results of periodate oxidation are in fair agreement with those of methylation studies.

After removing the iodate and periodate ions from the reaction mixture, the periodate-oxidised mannan was reduced with sodium borohydride and hydrolysed. Paper chromatographic examination of the hydrolysate revealed presence of glycerol and erythritol, which can be obtained from non-reducing ends and the 1 → 4 linked backbone units respectively. That at the branch points, the mannose residues are connected through C₁, C₄, and C₆ is proved further by absence of free sugar in the above hydrolysate.

The high negative specific rotation of the polysaccharide as well as its methylated derivative indicates predominance of β-linkages in the molecules.

It is therefore evident that the kernel of palm contains at least two homogeneous polysaccharides, viz., a galactomannan which can be extracted with water (Mukherjee *et al.*¹) and a mannan extractible with 18% NaOH solution, and with maturity the proportion of the former decreases but that of the latter increases. The polysaccharide material ex-

7. Rebers and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 6097.

8. Hirst and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1278.

9. Hirst *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 928.

tracted with 4% NaOH solution invariably showed a lower galactose to mannose ratio than did the galactomannan. This is perhaps a mixture of the two components mentioned above.

It is interesting to note that the nature of the backbone chain and that of the branch points are similar in both the galactomannan and the mannan varying in the lengths of the repeating units. The gradual enrichment of the mannan content of the kernel with maturity is considered to be highly significant. The question whether this takes place at the cost of the galactomannan (which contains no mannopyranose side groups) or whether the synthesis of the galactomannan and of the mannan are two independent processes, the former predominating in the tender stage and the latter in the mature stage, is now speculative.

EXPERIMENTAL

All specific rotations are equilibrium values. Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out in *vacuo* at 30-40°. The solvent mixtures (v/v) used for partition chromatography of sugars and their derivatives were:

- (A) Ethyl acetate: pyridine: water (8:2:1).
- (B) Methyl ethyl ketone—water azeotrope.
- (C) Butanol: acetic acid: water (4:1:5) (upper layer).
- (D) Butanol: ethanol: water (40:11:19).
- (E) Butanol: ethanol: water (4:1:5) (upper layer).

Whatman No. 1 filter papers were used for paper partition chromatography. The spray reagents used were: (a) aniline hydrogen oxalate (saturated aqueous solution) and (b) ammoniacal silver nitrate solution.

Isolation of the Polysaccharides

The hard kernel, obtained from the matured nut, was removed from the adhering brown layers and was macerated in a high speed "Kenmix 55" blender for 5 minutes in presence of ethanol. The resulting mass was kept overnight under ethanol, filtered through cloth, and dried. The dry material was then Soxhleted for 24 hours with ethanol-benzene (1:2, v/v) mixture to remove the oil and dried. The crude material (40 g.) was treated with water (1 litre) and heated with stirring on a boiling water bath for 5 hours. The resulting slurry was kept overnight and filtered through a piece of cloth. From the filtrate after supercentrifugation polysaccharide A was precipitated with ethanol. The residue was again treated in the same way as above. The residue from the second operation was extracted twice with 4% NaOH solution (500 ml each time) for 24 hours at room temperature while shaking in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The resulting mass was filtered through a piece of nylon cloth. The clear filtrate was acidified with acetic acid to pH 4-5 and added slowly to acetone (1500 ml) in the cold (0°-5°) to obtain polysaccharide B.

The residue, obtained after the above extraction process, was treated twice with 18% NaOH solution (500 ml each) in a similar manner and the clear filtrate was collected from each treatment. The combined filtrate was acidified with acetic acid to pH 4.5 in the cold (0-5°) and precipitated with acetone (1500 ml). The polysaccharides B and C were dialysed for 10 days against distilled water to remove the inorganic salts adhering and again precipitated with acetone. These were filtered, triturated with absolute ethanol and ether, and finally dried.

After obtaining the water-soluble polysaccharide (polysaccharide A) from the soft kernel of Palm nut, the residue was similarly treated to give polysaccharide B and polysaccharide C. A similar set of polysaccharides was isolated from medium hard nut. These polysaccharides were characterised. Table I records the characteristics of the polysaccharides A, B, and C of soft, medium hard, and hard kernels.

TABLE I

	Soft kernel.			Medium hard kernel.			Hard kernel.		
	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.
Yield(%)	25	7	3	15	8	0	1	3	30
Moisture(%)	10.0	9.6	10.2	8.7	9.8	10.1	9.2	10.4	9.6
Ash(%)	0.36	0.72	1.12	0.5	0.8	1.2	0.4	0.92	1.4
[α] _D	+8.5°	-15°	-42°	+9°	-12°	-43°	+6°	-16°	-43°
Pentosan (%) ¹⁰	0.5	0.4	0.54	0.32	0.42	0.6	0.15	0.56	0.36
Methoxyl(%) ¹⁰	0.3	0.24	0.42	0.60	0.28	0.40	0.50	0.38	0.48
Uronic acid (%) ¹¹	0.8	0.6	0.76	1.1	0.6	0.4	0.9	0.8	0.9
Galactose : mannose	1:2.4	1:10	Only man- nose	1:2.4	1:11	Only man- nose	1:2.1	1:10	Only man- nose
Arabinose(%)	..	..	..	..	..	..	6	..	..

[α]_D values were obtained for polysaccharides in 4% NaOH solution except in the case of polysaccharide C, for which 18% NaOH solution was used. Table I shows that the percentage of mannan increases with the age of the nut.

The polysaccharide C from the old nut (hitherto named as the mannan) was purified through complexing with Fehling's solution to afford the product showing [α]_D²⁰ -43°.

Hydrolysis and Identification of D-Mannose.—The mannan (0.5 g.) was kept with 72% H₂SO₄¹³ (2 ml) at room temperature overnight and brought to normal solution with respect to the acid by cautious addition of water (to avoid reprecipitation). The solution was heated on a boiling water bath when the hydrolysis was found to be complete (followed iodometrically¹⁴). The solution was neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered, passed through Amberlite IR-120 (H)^{*} and Amberlite IR-45 (OH)^{*}. The eluate was concentra-

10. C. Doree, "The Methods of Cellulose Chemistry", 2nd ed., Chapman & Hall Ltd., London, 1947, p. 381.

11. E.P. Clark, "Semimicro Quantitative Organic Analysis", Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1943, p. 68.

12. C. Doree, "The Methods of Cellulose Chemistry", 2nd ed., 1947, p.391.

13. Hamilton and Partlow, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4880.

14. Baker and Halton, *Biochem. J.*, 1920, **14**, 754.

*A product of Rohm & Haas Company, Pennsylvania, U.S.A.

ted to a syrup (480 mg.) containing chromatographically pure D-mannose, $[\alpha]_D^{20} +15$ in water (c, 1). This was converted into crystalline *p*-nitro-*N*-phenyl-D-mannosylamine by treatment with *p*-nitroaniline in acidified methanol¹⁵; m.p. and mixed m.p. 217-19° (Mukherjee *et al.*); $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, -324° in dry pyridine (c, 1) (lit.¹⁵, -325°).

Methylation of the Mannan.—The mannan (4g.) was methylated first by methyl sulphate and alkali and then by methyl iodide and silver oxide following the method of Falconer and Adams¹⁶. The methylated product (2.8 g., $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, -17° (in chloroform, c, 1) (Found: OMe, 42.8. Calc. for C₉H₁₆O₅: OMe, 44.7%) showed no hydroxyl absorption band in the IR spectrum.

Methanolysis and Hydrolysis of the Methylated Mannan.—A solution of the fully methylated mannan (0.7 g.) in 5% MeOH-HCl was refluxed (16 hours) till the rotation became constant. The solution was cooled and evaporated to a syrup under reduced pressure. The resulting mixture of methyl glycosides was hydrolysed with *N*-HCl (40 ml) for 14 hours (rotation constant). The solution was neutralised (silver carbonate), deionised with Amberlite I R-120(H) and amberlite I R-45 (OH), and concentrated to a syrup (0.58 g.).

A small portion of the syrup (ca. 5 mg.) was demethylated¹⁷ by heating for 5 minutes on a boiling water bath with 48% hydrobromic acid (2 ml) in a sealed tube in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The resulting solution after usual treatment gave a syrup which, on paper chromatographic analysis using solvent A, indicated presence of only D-mannose along with some partially demethylated sugars.

On paper chromatographic analysis using solvents B and D, the mixture of methyl sugars was separated into the following components (Table II).

TABLE II

Spot No.	*R ₀ (solvent D).	%OMe.	Sugars (O-Methyl-D-mannose).
1	0.96	51.1	2,3,4,6-Tetra.
2	0.82	42.0	2,3,6-Tri.
3	0.61	28.8	2,3-Di.

*R₀ values are with respect to 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose.

Separation and Characterisation of the Methyl Sugar

The mixture (ca. 300 mg.) separated on Whatman No. 3 MM filter papers using solvent D. The strips corresponding to the tetra-, tri-, and di-*O*-methyl sugars were cut, eluted quantitatively with water, evaporated to dryness, and weighed as: tetramethyl 29 mg., trimethyl, 229 mg., dimethyl 30.4 mg. All these components were chromatographically pure.⁸

The 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-mannose (OMe 51.1% (calc. for C₁₀H₂₀O₆: 52.5%)) $\left\{ [\alpha]_D^{20} +2^\circ \right.$ (in water c, 1) (lit.^{8,19} +3°; +2.40¹⁹) was converted to the crystalline anilide by

15. Weygand *et al.*, *Chem. Ber.* 1951, 84, 594.

16. *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1956, 34, 336; Adams, *ibid.*, 1958, 36, 755.

17. Hough *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1702.

18. Rao *et al.*, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1961, 39, 375.

19. Green and Lewis, *Science*, 1926, 64, 206; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2813.

refluxing with aniline in ethanol and recrystallising from ether-petroleum ether; m.p. and mixed m.p. 142-143° (lit. m.p. 143-44°); $[\alpha]_D^{20} -38^\circ$ (in acetone).

The tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose {OMe 42.0% (calc. for $C_6H_{12}O_6$: OMe, 41.9%), $[\alpha]_D^{20} -9^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ (in water; *c*, 1)} was converted to 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose-1,4-di-*p*-nitrobenzoate by treatment with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride in pyridine²⁰ and recrystallisation from methanol; m.p. and mixed m.p. 189-90°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +33^\circ$ (in chloroform, *c*, 0.5).

The di-*O*-methylmannose having OMe, 28.8% (calc. for $C_6H_{12}O_6$: OMe, 29.8%), $[\alpha]_D^{20} -15^\circ$ (in water; *c*, 0.5) and $+9^\circ$ (in ethanol; *c*, 0.5) was oxidised with bromine water and the lactone²¹ obtained was converted into the 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-mannonic acid phenylhydrazide which was crystallised from methanol-ether, m.p. 158-60°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} -25^\circ$ (in water; *c*, 0.5).

A small portion of the mixture was quantitatively separated on a paper chromatogram and the components estimated by alkaline hypoiodite titration⁹. The tetra-, tri- and di-methylmannoses were found in the molar ratio of 1:8.15:1.12.

Periodate Oxidation of the Mannan.—The polysaccharide (120 mg.) was allowed to disperse in water (50 ml) and was oxidised with 0.1*M* sodium metaperiodate solution (50 ml). The reaction was conducted by shaking the mixture in dark at 15°. The liberated formic acid and the consumption of periodate were estimated in the usual way²² at regular intervals of time. After 25 hours the liberation of formic acid became constant, corresponding to 9.7 hexose residues per mole of formic acid. At the same time the consumption of periodate also became constant, corresponding to 1.05 moles of the oxidant per mole of anhydrohexose residues.

Reduction of the Oxidised Mannan.—The periodate-oxidised product was neutralised with barium hydroxide, filtered, and the clear filtrate was reduced with sodium borohydride (200 mg.) at room temperature for 4 hours. The resulting solution was acidified with acetic acid, hydrolysed, and after usual treatments²³ concentrated to a syrup which on paper chromatography, using solvent E and ammoniacal silver nitrate spray, showed presence of only glycerol and erythritol. The mixture was separated on Whatman No. 3 MM filter papers using solvent E. The zones corresponding to glycerol and erythritol were eluted and concentrated to syrups. These were characterised through their tri- and tetra-tosyl derivatives respectively. The tri-tosylglycerol had m.p. and mixed m.p. 101-102°, and the tetra-tosylerythritol had m.p. and mixed m.p. 164-65°.

The authors are thankful to Dr. P. Bagchi, Director, Research, East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., Calcutta, for valuable advice and interest in this paper.

DEPARTMENT OF MACROMOLECULES,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA-32.

Received April 30, 1962.

20. Rebers and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 8097.

21. Smith, *ibid.*, 1949, **70**, 3249.

22. Fleury and Junge, *J. pharm. chim.*, 1933, *viii*, **17**, 107.

23. Smith and Srivastava, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1715.